
**GRAPHENE BASED NANOCOMPLEXES CAN BE RATIONALLY MODIFIED
WITH A VARIETY OF FUNCTIONAL COMPOUNDS TO IMPROVE
THERAPEUTIC EFFECTIVENESS INCLUDING GENE THERAPY**

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Abstract

Graphene-family nanomaterials (GFNs)-based nanocomplexes have been hailed as a rising star in the field of nanomaterials. GFNs can be rationally modified with a variety of functional chemicals to improve therapeutic effectiveness. The active targeted drug delivery of GFNs is facilitated by conjugating with particular targeting ligands. A phototherapy method combining GFNs and PSs that may cause the formation of ROS with the help of NIR light irradiation, for example, has been shown to be effective in PTT. GFNs can cause cellular injuries such as cytoskeletal disorders, organelle dysfunction, protein corona damage, and damage to biological macromolecules after being absorbed into the human body. To decrease the toxicity of GFNs, biocompatible polymers such as peptides, PEG, hyperbranched polyglycerol, -cyclodextrin, and a variety of polysaccharides have been used. When combined with successful treatment methods, GFNs have the potential to be used in a range of clinical applications in biomedicine, including biosensing, bioimaging, tissue engineering, and medication delivery. However, success in translating GFNs-based nanocomplexes from the bench to the bedside remains a long way off.

1. Introduction

Graphene is a two-dimensional monolayer of sp²-hybridized carbon atoms in a honeycomb lattice that was discovered by Andre Geim and Konstantin Novoselov, who were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 2004, [1]. Graphene may be used as a building block to make fullerenes (0-dimension), carbon nanotubes (1-dimension), and graphite (3-dimension) due to its unique structure [2]. More significantly, graphene has unique physical and chemical characteristics, including a huge specific surface area, high Young's modulus and fracture strength, outstanding electrical and thermal conductivity, and optical absorption. Graphene-family nanomaterials (GFNs) have sparked interest in a variety of disciplines since their discovery, including quantum physics [3], photocatalysis [4], electrocatalysis [5], battery generation [6], thermal conductivity [7], bio-imaging [8], biosensor [9], and tissue engineering [10].

Graphene oxide (GO) is one of the most important graphene derivatives, and it is made by reacting graphite with a strong acid and an oxidizing agent [11]. As a result, a variety of oxygen-containing functional groups, including carboxyl, epoxy, and hydroxyl groups, are added to the surface of GO, especially near the edge [12]. Because GO has enough oxygen-containing functional groups, it may be covalently modified with a variety of hydrophilic and

biocompatible compounds [13], improving its solubility and lowering its toxicity. Furthermore, GO can load hydrophobic medicines via stacking and hydrophobic interactions due to free electrons on the surface [14,15]. Other non-covalent interactions, including the Van der Waals force, electrostatic contact, hydrogen bond, and ionic bond, might also be used to modify GO [16–18]. However, because GO has a higher oxygen-to-carbon ratio, it has poorer conductivity and optical absorption [19]. Reduced GO (RGO) was created by partially reducing GO using reducing agents or a hydrothermal reduction technique to preserve these properties while retaining a specific number of oxygen-containing groups. In addition, graphene quantum dots (GQDs) are a type of graphene derivative that can be made using one of two methods: top-down (acidic exfoliation and oxidation, hydrothermal synthesis, microwave-assisted synthesis, electrochemical oxidation) or bottom-up (pyrolysis or carbonization methods, stepwise organic synthesis) [20]. Similarly, GQDs are widely employed in the area of biomedicine [21]. Although GFNs have several benefits in drug administration, they face a number of challenges in clinical use, including biological toxicity and low solubility [22]. Pristine graphene, for example, has a large surface area (2600 m²/g) and a high drug loading, yet it can not dissolve in physiological fluids due to the carbon atoms' strong bonding [23]. Because there are enough hydrophilic oxygen-containing functional groups in GO, it is more hydrophilic than pure graphene. However, it is still unable to diffuse uniformly in biological solutions. High dosages of GFNs have been shown to induce significant toxicity, including pulmonary inflammation, acute lung injury, pulmonary edema, poor cell viability, protein corona, and enhanced DNA damage due to the production of excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) [24–27], among other things. As a result, the clinical use of GFNs remains a significant issue. The studies on GFN toxicity have been effectively summarized in numerous published review papers [28–30], so they will not be discussed in depth in this review.

To solve this issue, a variety of approaches have been used. The most popular method is to functionalize graphene with polyethylene glycol (PEG) or other biocompatible chemicals to make GFNs more biocompatible. The introduction of modified GFNs has paved the way for novel applications of GFN-based nanocomplexes in the medical field. Dai and colleagues were the first to show that modified graphene could be used as a drug delivery vehicle in 2008 [31,32]. Since then, GFNs have been widely used in medical science and biological technology, including drug delivery, in vivo biological sensing, in vivo biological imaging, tissue engineering, and antimicrobial materials [29,35–37]. GFNs, including GO and RGO, as well as GQDs [33] and graphene nanoribbons [34], have been widely used in medical science and biological technology, including drug delivery, in vivo biological sensing, in vivo biological imaging. The drug-loading efficiency of GFNs is significantly greater than that of other nanoparticle-based drug carriers [38] due to their huge relative specific surface area. As a result, it's no surprise that GFNs can readily be conjugated with medicines and some functional molecules, making them one of the best drug delivery options. Furthermore, in the last few years, site-specific drug delivery methods have been extensively researched in order to increase the therapeutic impact of GFNs while reducing toxicity in normal tissues [39,40]. GFNs are frequently utilized in photothermal treatment (PTT) [41] with the irradiation of near-infrared (NIR) light due to their superior optical absorption and photothermal conversion. Meanwhile, using photosensitizer to decorate GFNs allows for effective photodynamic treatment (PDT) [42]. Furthermore, combining PDT and PTT may significantly improve their therapeutic

efficacy [43]. Despite the fact that numerous reviews on GFNs have been published [23,28,40, 44–50], this review focuses on the advancements and development in the application of GFNs to drug delivery, including diverse strategies for improving biocompatibility, specific targeting and stimuli-responsiveness of GFNs for drug delivery, and drug and gene codelivery. In addition, we looked at current papers on PTT, PDT, and GFN-based multimodal combination treatment.

2. The utilization of GFNs in medication delivery

GFNs-based drug carriers have been widely researched due to their remarkable physical and chemical characteristics, which have accompanied the enormous development of nanomaterials for decades. GFNs have a lot of potential in drug delivery because of their 2D planar shape and hydrophobic surface, which is rich in delocalized electrons. GFNs may encapsulate a variety of molecules, such as hydrophobic drugs, macromolecule polymers, peptides, antibodies, and genes, using a combination of stacking, hydrophobic contact, electrostatic interaction, and physical absorption [51–53]. GO might be conjugated with amino-containing compounds via amide linkage in addition to non-covalent interactions [13,54]. Despite their high drug loading capacity, GFNs cluster quickly in biological solutions when divalent cations (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) are present [55]. Furthermore, due to its sharp edge, pure graphene is prone to triggering an inflammatory response, generating excess ROS, and destroying normal cells. Because they contain certain hydrophilic functional groups, GO and RGO are more biocompatible than graphene, with surface diameters ranging from the nanoscale to microns. They may, however, induce cell toxicity at large concentrations [56], particularly for RGO. The toxicity of nanosized GO and RGO platelets with surface diameters ranging from 100 nm to 10 μm was studied by Jaworski et al. RGO's cell viability on U87 and U118 human cell lines was shown to be significantly lower than that of GO-treated cells at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ [57]. Jia and colleagues have examined the toxicity of graphene and GO in three distinct sizes: big (several microns), medium (hundreds of nanometers), and tiny (a few microns) (tens of nanometers). The toxicity of graphene was found to be substantially greater than that of GO, with small-sized graphene and GO exhibiting more severe toxicity than medium- and large-sized materials [27]. More significantly, the therapeutic efficacy of GFNs is hampered by their inability to target particular diseased areas. All of the disadvantages have become roadblocks to their clinical use. As a result, more reasonable and new techniques are required to attain favorable biocompatibility and adequate effectiveness. We review the many techniques for enhancing biocompatibility, precise targeting, and stimuli-responsive GFNs, as well as medication and gene code delivery, in this section.

2.1. GFN biocompatibility

As previously stated, limited biocompatibility is a major impediment to bringing GFNs from the bench to the bedside. Singh and coworkers were the first to synthesize amine-functionalized graphene to tackle this challenge, which had greater biocompatibility and had no effect on human platelets than GO [58]. Polymeric modification using friendly and nontoxic chemicals is very enticing, particularly when nonionic polymer surfactants are used. Because of its advantageous properties, such as high biocompatibility, good solubility, adequate biodegradability, and great conformational flexibility to avoid blood protein binding, PEG has been the most widely utilized polymer for the modification of GFNs [59]. PEGylated GFNs

have been shown to have good drug loading capacity, high cellular uptake capacity, and decreased cytotoxicity in several studies [60–63].

Dai and coworkers were the first to effectively graft PEG onto the surface and edge of nano-GO for hydrophobic drug delivery [32]. They discovered that the combination was extremely stable and soluble in a biological solution, and that it did not cause any cytotoxicity. Hyperbranched polyglycerol is another notable nonionic surfactant that has similar biocompatibility and solubility as PEG. Mu and colleagues developed hyperbranched polyglycerol-GO as an effective anticancer drug carrier with low toxicity and no effect on blood coagulation or hemolysis [64]. Tween 80 and Pluronic F38 are also commonly utilized in the construction of GFN-based vehicles because they can prevent nanoparticle aggregation and therefore improve biocompatibility. The two nonionic surfactants can be esterified with the carboxylic groups of GO because of the hydroxyl-rich structure. Kakran et al., for example, functionalized GO with Tween 80 and Pluronic F38 through an ester link to transport the insoluble medicine ellagic acid. The two GO-based alterations were effectively distributed in the buffer solution compared to pure GO, with no significant cytotoxicity to the HT29 and MCF7 cell lines [65]. Aside from nonionic surfactants, anionic surfactants have also been suggested as a viable strategy for improving GFN biocompatibility. Wang and colleagues, for example, used the π -stacking interaction to modify RGO using the anionic surfactant poly (sodium 4-styrenesulfonate). According to the results of the CCK-8 experiment [66], the necessary nano-composites had good biocompatibility. Zhang and colleagues used both nonionic and anionic surfactants to alter GO to create a nanocarrier to transport doxorubicin (DOX) under the direction of the nonideal mixed micelle theory. Even at a high dosage of 212.31 g/mL, the obtained nanocarrier was shown to be virtually completely secure for SKOV3 cells [67].

Furthermore, additional biocompatible materials may play an important role in improving GFN biocompatibility. A good example is polysaccharide, which has excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability. GFNs treated with polysaccharides have greater biocompatibility and toxicity. Furthermore, polysaccharide modification might improve GFN water dispersibility. Deng et al. used a layer-by-layer method to cover graphene with polysaccharides (chitosan, sodium alginate, and hyaluronic acid) to create a 'micro-Matryoshka'-like biocompatible hybrid microcapsule. The obtained microcapsules showed no cytotoxicity in HeLa cells, according to the results of the CCK-8 experiment [68]. A fucose-rich sulfated polysaccharide was used by another group to alter RGO (termed as Fu-RGO). Fu-RGO was discovered to have good biocompatibility and water dispersibility. In co-cultured cell cultures, fluorescence pictures revealed that Fu-RGO could selectively kill tumor cells while having no effect on HEK 293 T cells [69]. Hyaluronic acid (HA) is also a superior linear polysaccharide with outstanding biodegradability and biocompatibility. To reduce GO's sharp edge, Zhang and colleagues used a mediator, polyetheramine, to coat it with HA. Even at a high concentration of 350 g/mL, the nanocomposites generated minimal hemolysis and cytotoxicity, according to the findings [54].

GFNs might be used for gene therapy in addition to medication delivery. Saravanabhavan and colleagues, for example, used covalent bonding to graft chitosan (CS) onto the surface of GO for siRNA complexation. In three distinct cell lines, they discovered that the gene carrier had no cytotoxicity [70]. β -Cyclodextrin, an FDA-approved oligosaccharide, was likewise grafted

onto graphene. The -cyclodextrin-modified GFNs were shown to have improved blood compatibility [71], good biocompatibility, and increased water-dispersibility [72,73]. Other materials, such as peptide [74–76], polydopamine [77], human serum albumin [78], heparin [79], bovine alpha-lactalbumin [80], poly (allylamine hydrochloride) [81], glycyrrhetic acid [82], nanoscale hydroxyapatite [83], carboxyl moieties with ethylene diamine [84], and polylactin [85], have also been shown to

2.2. GFNs' ability to target

It is widely established that therapeutic drug uptake in aberrant diseased areas can significantly improve therapeutic efficacy while avoiding adverse effects produced by nonspecific uptake in normal cells [86]. GFNs can easily pass through micro-circulatory channels and collect in these locations due to their unique size and 2D design, especially for those with diameters of less than 200 nm [87–89]. This process is aided by the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, which promotes long-term blood circulation and increased vascular permeability around the tumor [90]. The EPR effect, on the other hand, exhibits variability among tumor types, suggesting that it can not be regarded as a universal feature of solid tumors [91]. Although the use of a passive targeting technique has had some success in clinical studies, it still falls short of meeting the need for site-specific medication delivery. Active targeted drug delivery, on the other hand, has been hailed as a potential approach for preventing nonspecific accumulation, poor cellular internalization, and high drug efflux in GFN-based drug delivery systems. For efficient drug administration, GFNs are frequently modified with targeting ligands that have high affinity for the particular receptors overexpressed on the surface of targeted cells [92,93]. Antibodies, aptamers, peptides, and other natural compounds are among the many targeting moieties employed in the modification of GFNs. Skin cancer, breast cancer, pancreatic cancer, mammary cancer, colorectal cancer, ovary cancer, brain cancer, gastric cancer, lung cancer, and glioblastoma have all been shown to have overexpressed epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) on their surfaces [94]. As a result, EGFR antibodies are frequently employed in GFN modifications. scFvB10, for example, is a single-chain EGFR antibody fragment that may be attached to GQDs through an amide linkage. The cellular absorption of scFvB10-GQDs was stated to be much higher than that of free GQDs [95]. Sung and colleagues produced EGFR-targeted nanocomplexes by covering GQDs/docetaxel nanosponges with cetuximab-anchored red blood cell membrane. The tumor-targeting and penetrating capabilities of the biocompatible nanocomplexes were exceptional. The nanocomplexes were reported to have a high affinity for the EGFR receptor overexpressed on A549 cells, but poor cellular uptake in RAW 264.7 cells. More significantly, the cetuximab-anchored nanocomplexes accumulated 60 percent more in the tumor than the cetuximab-free nanocomplexes [96].

Aside from antibodies, a number of ligands, such as sulforaphane [97] and the GE11 peptide [98], have a high affinity for EGFR receptors. CD44 is a highly expressed receptor in tumor cells, similar to the EGFR receptor. HA is one of the most widely used ligands for tumor targeting via the CD44 receptor. In HeLa cells, HA-conjugated GQDs were shown to cause a significant buildup of DOX. Meanwhile, when compared to free DOX, DOX localisation in the nucleus was dramatically enhanced [99]. In addition, folic acid (FA)-functionalized GFNs have attracted a lot of interest as a tumor-targeting tool. Li's group, for example, developed FA-modified GO nanocomplexes for the delivery of K-Ras and HDAC1 siRNAs. The nanocomplexes were reported to be able to bind the overexpressed folate receptor (Fr) in MCF-

7 and MIA PaCa-2 cells and generate exceptionally high gene transfection efficiency [100]. The surface modification of GO with glycyrrhetic acid, which can efficiently interact with the respiratory chain of mitochondria, was used to produce a mitochondria-targeting nanocarrier for the delivery of DOX. The findings revealed that the manufactured nanocarrier may significantly improve mitochondrial permeability and successfully transport DOX into mitochondria, resulting in remarkable anticancer efficacy [101]. Several investigations have shown that inflammatory macrophages, in addition to tumor cells, may express FR selectively [102]. As a result, Fr-mediated targeted treatment can be used to treat inflammation. Han and colleagues, for example, coupled FA-PEG with PEI-modified GO for the delivery of IL-4 plasmid DNA. The vector internalization in macrophages was 7-fold greater than in cardiomyocytes and cardiac fibroblasts, as predicted. Most notably, it showed that the constructed vector was capable of converting inflammatory M1 macrophages to anti-inflammatory M2 phenotypes, reducing excessive ROS and activating the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines (e.g. IL-4 and IL-10) [103]. Other illnesses, such as brain damage [104], bone defects [105], and coagulation-related angiocardopathy [106], have been shown to benefit from particular ligand-modified GFNs.

2.3. GFNs that respond to stimuli

Apart from focused treatment methods, much work has gone into the development of smart nanosystems, which are GFN-based stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems [107]. Smart nanosystems are capable of retaining integrity in a normal environment while responding to a specific signal to correctly and effectively release therapeutic chemicals in targeted locations [108]. As a result, this method can effectively address the drawbacks of traditional delivery systems, such as premature cargo release during circulation and uncontrolled cargo release in sick areas [109]. In general, several endogenous variables (e.g. pH [110], redox potential [111], and biomolecule [112]) or physical stimuli can trigger contemporary GFNs-based drug delivery systems (e.g. thermo [113], light [114], magnetic field [115], ultrasound [116] and electricity [117]). The smart nanosystem can spatially and temporally manage the release of therapeutic cargos to diseased areas with the help of those triggers.

2.3.1. GFNs that respond to endogenous stimuli

2.3.1.1 pH-responsive GFNs

The pH-responsive technique has been the most popular way of designing GFNs-based stimuli-responsive drug delivery devices in recent years. In general, the pH levels of various tissues change noticeably between healthy and diseased conditions [118]. The pH of normal tissues, for example, remains constant at around 7.4. Certain pathological conditions, including ischemia, infection, diabetes, inflammation, and cancer, have a higher acidic pH [119–121]. The acidic microenvironment of tumor tissues (pH = 6.5–7.2) is attributed, for example, to increased lactic acid production as a result of tumor cell growth without sufficient oxygen and nutrients [101]. Furthermore, the pH values of distinct intracellular organelles, such as endosomes (pH = 5.5–6.0), lysosomes (pH = 4.5–5.0), and cytosol (pH = 7.4), are all different [122].

A growing variety of GFNs-based pH-responsive drug delivery devices have been developed in response to various pH situations. pH-responsive nanosystems are often divided into two groups [121]. Conjugating GFNs with molecules possessing ionizable functional groups, such as carboxylic acids, basic amines, sulfonic acids, and acidic phosphoric acids, is a common

strategy [122]. When the pH of the surrounding medium lowers, the molecules become ionized, triggering cargo release as a result of cargo and vector instability or dissociation [93,123]. Abbasian et al., for example, created a pH-responsive GO-based nanoparticle with a DOX payload made of CS-graft-poly (methacrylic acid) and GO. In vitro drug release findings indicated that almost 80% of DOX was released in an acidic buffer (pH 4) at the same time, but only 25% of DOX was released in a physiological solution. The protonation of the drug's -NH₂ groups, which hindered the π -stacking interaction between DOX and the vector in the acidic environment, may be to blame for the pH-triggered drug release profile. Furthermore, the MTT experiment revealed that MCF-7 had decreased cell viability after being treated with the nanoparticle [124]. Zhao et al. created a pH-responsive surface charge-reversible drug delivery system based on GO by electrostatically coating the GO core with CS and dimethylmaleic anhydride-modified CS. The CS-based shell was shown to be capable of preventing payloads from being released prematurely in a typical extracellular environment. However, the removal of the CS coating resulted in increased drug release in slightly acidic conditions (pH = 5.0) [125]. Another successful method is to alter GFNs by utilizing acid-labile linkers to conjugate cargos, such as hydrazine, imine, acetal, boronate ester, orthoester, and so on [126]. In an acidic environment, these acid-labile bonds can be quickly broken, yet they stay stable in a physiological environment. Pourjavadi and colleagues, for example, created a pH-responsive nanocarrier by using Fe₃O₄ modified polyamidoamine dendrimers to decorate the borders of GO sheets for the transport of DOX and curcumin via hydrazone linkage and π -stacking interaction.

Due to the hydrolysis of hydrazone bonds, 80 percent of DOX was released in an acidic buffer solution (pH 5.0) after 72 hours, whereas only 37 percent of DOX was released at pH 7.4. The higher the concentration of DOX in the buffer solution, the faster the release of curcumin, suggesting that DOX may have a role in curcumin solubility in the aqueous medium. Furthermore, higher concentrations of the codelivery system resulted in apparent cytotoxicity against MCF-7 cells [127].

2.3.1 Redox-responsive GFNs

The redox-responsive nanosystem, in addition to the pH-responsive approach, is one of the most common responsive drug delivery technologies [128]. It is well acknowledged that glutathione (GSH) plays an important function in mammalian cells, as it is capable of scavenging electrophilic chemicals and free radicals (e.g. ROS), as well as maintaining cellular microenvironment redox homeostasis [129]. Previous studies have shown that the concentration of GSH inside the cell (1–20 mM) is 1000 times higher than that seen in the extracellular environment. GSH levels in the cytoplasm of cancer cells are around 4-fold greater than in normal cells [130]. Obviously, a high GSH content within tumor cells may be used as a signal to develop a GFNs-based smart nanosystem that can respond to GSH and avoid premature medication release in the systemic circulation. Through GSH-cleavable linkers, particularly disulfide bonds, multiple polymers, polysaccharides, proteins, or amino acids are used to build the GFNs-based smart nanosystem [131–134]. Zhao et al. used disulfide bonds to attach the detachable cyamine conjugated PEGylated alginate brushes onto GO nanoparticles. By using the stacking interaction, the obtained nanoparticle was used to encapsulate DOX. The CLSM investigation found that after 6 hours of incubation in the presence of 10 mM GSH, DOX was fully released into the cytoplasm of HepG2 cells,

suggesting that the disulfide linkage was rapidly cleaved. Furthermore, in the presence of GSH, a strong cytotoxic impact on HepG2 was found [135]. In another study, Liu and colleagues used disulfide bonds to join GO and HA to create a gefitinib-loaded drug delivery system, which improved anticancer efficiency. The strong affinity between HA and CD44 receptors resulted in a significant increase in carrier endocytosis in A549 cells, as demonstrated by a cellular uptake experiment. More interestingly, they discovered that under 10 mM GSH, the drug release rate appeared to be increased. In A549 tumor cell-bearing mice, the carrier had a greater impact on inhibiting the development of the solid tumor than the free drug [133].

Unlike GSH, ROS is a redox-active species that is produced throughout the cell's metabolic process. Superoxide (O_2^-), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), hydroxyl radicals ($HO^\bullet$), hypochlorous acid ($HClO$), and singlet oxygen ($^1O_2$) are examples of ROS, which are found throughout the body and engage in a variety of signaling pathways [136]. Excessive ROS can induce the breakdown of numerous critical macromolecules (e.g. DNA and proteins) due to significant oxidative stress [137], resulting in pathological diseases such as cancer, diabetes, neurodegenerative illnesses, chronic inflammation, and cardiovascular disease [138].

ROS-responsive nanocarriers based on GFNs have been created as a result of the differences in ROS levels between normal and pathologic tissue. However, the distribution of ROS in the pathologic microenvironment is not necessarily uniform [139]. In order to ensure full and accurate medication release in such a circumstance, photosensitizer was put into the nanocarrier to enhance the ROS level in the diseased tissue following NIR light irradiation. The comprehensive examples were provided in the PDT section.

2.3.1 GFNs that respond to biomolecules

It is widely known that the high concentrations of certain biomolecules seen in sick areas can be utilized to build medication delivery devices that are biomolecule-responsive. In several studies, biomolecules such as glucose [140], adenosine-5-triphosphate (ATP) [141], cathepsin [142], metalloproteinases [143], hyaluronidase [144], furin [145], and fibroblast activation protein [146] have been considered. For example, ATP is a critical biogenic energy source for mammalian cells and is concentrated in intracellular compartments (1-10 mM) rather than in the external environment [147]. Furthermore, it has been discovered that the amount of ATP in tumor cells has significantly increased [148]. Zheng et al. have developed a smart nanocarrier for ATP-dependent drug release by immobilizing GQDs onto the surface of a fluorescent mesoporous silica nanoparticle using an ATP aptamer. PEG and AS1411 aptamers were additionally attached to the nanoparticle's surface to improve biocompatibility and endocytosis, respectively. In the presence of adequate ATP, faster drug release was seen, which was ascribed to the interaction between ATP and the ATP aptamer. Furthermore, the nanocarrier was shown to have a greater lethality against Hela cells than the one without the ATP aptamer [149]. In the same way, the biomolecule-responsive approach has been used to treat bacterial infections. Some bacteria (e.g., *S. aureus*) have been found to overproduce hyaluronidase [150], prompting researchers to construct enzyme-responsive nanocarriers. Ji and colleagues created a hyaluronidase-responsive 'on-demand' drug delivery system in 2016 by encapsulating ascorbic acid in a sandwich-like graphene-mesoporous silica nanosheet capped with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles modified with HA-dopamine. They discovered that in the presence of hyaluronidase, disassociation of the capped HA-dopamine allowed approximately

73 percent of ascorbic acid to be liberated from the carrier. The notable antibacterial activity was obtained at a very low concentration without drug resistance, as predicted [151].

2.3.2. GFNs that respond to exogenous stimuli

External stimuli (e.g. light irradiation, electric field ultrasound, and temperature) with the use of particular physical stimuli are more steady, controlled, and efficient than internal stimuli. The magnetic field, often known as the "invisible hand," has been widely used in the development of drug carriers for particular drug delivery [152]. The magnetic field, unlike other physical stimuli, is mild for the human body [153].

As a result, it is recognized as one of the most effective physical stimuli. Meanwhile, it's worth emphasizing that, in most situations, the exogenous magnetic field simply draws the nanocarriers to the targets rather than altering the payloads' release behavior. GFNs are capable of absorbing different magnetic nanoparticles on the surface due to their inherent feature of large specific surface area. When coupled with GFNs for site-specific drug administration, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (e.g. Fe₃O₄) are a suitable component for forming a magnetic-responsive smart system [154]. Lu and colleagues recently used chemical coprecipitation to effectively manufacture a superparamagnetic Fe₃O₄-GO composite that was coupled with PEG and cetuximab for efficient DOX administration. The nanocomposite has dual magnetic and active targeting characteristics thanks to the Fe₃O₄ alteration and cetuximab. The nanocomposite performed admirably in terms of site-specific drug delivery and antitumor effectiveness [155]. Shirvalilou et al. created nanoparticles made of GO and modified poly lactic-co-glycolic acid with superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles for magnetic targeted delivery of 5-iodo-2-deoxyuridine. The nanoparticles were preferentially deposited in rat glioma sites in the presence of an external magnetic field, according to MRI scans. Meanwhile, glioma-bearing rats' median survival time was clearly extended [156]. Aside from focused drug delivery, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles are thought to be a suitable material for producing magnetic hyperthermia using an alternating magnetic field, which might be used in hyperthermia cancer therapy to improve therapeutic efficiency. Rodrigues and colleagues, for example, created a multifunctional drug delivery system with a DOX payload made of graphene, Fe₃O₄, and pluronic F-127. The produced nanocomposites displayed moderate hyperthermia in a 340 kHz alternating magnetic field for 30 minutes, resulting in rapid drug release and high cytotoxicity in human liver cancer cells [157]. GFNs functionalized with superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles have also been used in various biomedical applications, such as magnetic resonance imaging and cellular capture and isolation [158].

2.3.2 Thermo-responsive GFNs

The temperature gradient between healthy tissues (37°C) and pathological tissues (40–42°C) exposed to pyrogens or pathogens, such as inflammation and malignancy, is well-known [159]. As a result, a lot of research has gone into developing temperature-triggered medication delivery devices. Nonetheless, a temperature difference of this magnitude is not always visible. As a result, the use of an external heating source has become more frequent. A large amount of research on creating GFNs-based smart nanosystems activated by an external heating source has been carried out using heat-sensitive compounds [153,160]. When the temperature is below the lower critical solution temperature (LCST = 32°C), poly (N-isopropylacrylamide)

(PNIPAM), one of the most well-known heat-sensitive polymers, is water-soluble, and vice versa [161,162].

Because the LCST of pure PNIPAM is lower than normal body temperature, some particular chemicals have been bestowed with the ability to change with PNIPAM, allowing the LCST to be adjusted. By crosslinking PNIPAM, acrylic acid, and salep-modified GO, Bardajee and colleagues created a temperature- and pH-responsive nanogel. DOX was entrapped in the nanogel through hydrogen bonding. When the temperature was elevated from 37°C to 42°C, the release rate of DOX was substantially enhanced, resulting in a powerful potency to kill HeLa cells. This is most likely due to hydrogen bond breakage produced by the transition of PNIPAM from a hydrophile to a hydrophobic state at a temperature greater than its LCST [163]. Wang et al. [164] made a similar observation as well. They made thermo-sensitive nanohybrids by covalently gluing PNIPAM-poly (ethylene oxide) to GO nanosheets for DOX administration. The LCST of the nanohybrid was 34.8°C, which was greater than that of pure PNIPAM. When the temperature was raised to 37°C, approximately 22% of DOX was released from the nanohybrid. Furthermore, the produced nanohybrid was shown to have a remarkable capacity to destroy HepG2 cells. Poly (N-vinylcaprolactam) (PNVCL), a nontoxic heat-sensitive material similar to PNIPAM, has also gotten a lot of interest. Kazempour and colleagues used poly (glycolic acid) to upregulate PNVCL's LCST from 32 to 37 degrees Celsius. Modifying GO with PNVCL-poly (glycolic acid) resulted in a biocompatible and biodegradable nanocarrier with dual thermo- and pH-responsive profiles [165]. All of these examples demonstrate the enormous potential of GFN-based thermo-responsive nanosystems in biomedical applications. The indirect hyperthermia effect induced by NIR irradiation was used in addition to direct heating (e.g. water bath). The photothermal energy conversion of GFNs following NIR irradiation is discussed more in the part of the PTT below.

2.3.2 Other GFNs that respond to stimuli

External stimuli such as ultrasound, electricity, and light have also been used as alternative triggers in the development of remote-controlled medication delivery systems. Ultrasound may be used to produce smart medication release behavior in an ultrasound-responsive system (at least 1 MHz). Li and colleagues, for example, used the electrospray technique to encapsulate DOX in Fe₃O₄/GO/CS microspheres. The drug release behavior remained consistent due to the homogeneous distribution of DOX throughout the microsphere covered by the CS matrix. Surprisingly, under ultrasonography, the rate of DOX release was substantially increased [166]. Furthermore, bubbles and hyperthermia generated by ultrasound have been shown to enhance the permeability of biological membranes, allowing nanocarriers to be taken up by cells [123,167]. GFNs with good electrical conductivity have also been used in the creation of an effective 'switch on-off' drug delivery system controlled by electrical activation, in addition to the techniques outlined above. Yun and colleagues recently used Ca²⁺ as a crosslinker to create a crosslinking sodium alginate-GO nanocarrier. The faster drug release was found in the presence of an external electric field, due to GO's exceptional electro-conductivity and enhanced electrostatic repulsion with the drug [168].

2.3.3. Drug and gene delivery based on GFNs

Combination treatment using a chemical medication and a gene can maximize the therapeutic impact of both agents [169]. The Bcl-2 protein, for example, has long been thought to be linked to tumor cells' multidrug resistance (MDR) impact. Zhang's team was the first to use PEI-GO nanocomplexes to distribute Bcl-2 siRNA and DOX in a sequential manner. The nanocomplexes were shown to be capable of bypassing the MDR effect, resulting in a synergistic anticancer impact on HeLa cells [170]. Despite the therapeutic impact of both agents being combined, sequential drug and gene delivery utilizing two different vectors fails to achieve synchronized bio-distribution and pharmacokinetics for both therapeutic agents [169]. GFNs-based co-delivery systems, which enable the simultaneous delivery of two cargos into the same cell, have piqued interest in recent years as a solution to this challenge. The majority of them were devoted to cancer treatment [171]. The VEGF protein, for example, has been shown to be overexpressed in tumors linked to pathophysiological vascular abnormalities [172]. Sun and coauthors created a new biocompatible carrier for the co-delivery of DOX and anti-VEGF siRNA to produce a synergistic anticancer effect by connecting FA-modified poly-L-lysine with GO. The siRNA and DOX were promptly released from the carrier and accumulated in the cytoplasm and nucleus, respectively, after the carrier entered the HeLa cells. The synergistic anticancer impact on tumor development was seen, as predicted [173]. Furthermore, Let-7 g miRNA has been identified as a tumor-suppressor gene that inhibits Ras oncogene expression [174]. Yang and colleagues used poly (amidoamine) and gadolinium-functionalized GO to administer epirubicin and Let-7 g miRNA at the same time. When compared to a single-drug therapy, the codelivery method exhibited greater transfection efficiency and more effective suppression of human glioblastoma (U87) cell growth. More intriguingly, the codelivery method may be used as a contrast agent to monitor the opening area of the blood-brain barrier and quantify the amount of medicine delivered into the brain under the influence of an external magnetic field [175].

3 Phototherapy

Aside from medication delivery, GFNs might be utilized in phototherapy (i.e. PTT and PDT), which is a potential therapeutic approach for treating a variety of illnesses due to its capacity to regulate disease by precise light irradiation [47,50,176]. GFNs have a lot of potential in the field of biomedical research because of their particular spatiotemporal selectivity and low invasiveness of phototherapy [177–179]. The two distinct methods of phototherapy based on GFNs are explained in depth in the sections that follow.

3.1. PTT

PTT is a controllable and minimally invasive method that can absorb specific NIR (750–1000 nm) laser irradiation to generate excessive heat, resulting in abnormal cell death due to changes in cell membrane permeability and intracellular enzyme activity at temperatures ranging from 41°C to 47°C, or cell membrane injury and protein denaturation at temperatures ranging from 41°C to 47°C.

Because of their high optical absorption and photothermal conversion capacity in the NIR region, GFNs have garnered a lot of attention in the field of PTT treatment in recent years [49,178,184–186]. The use of GO for PTT treatment was originally described by Liu and his team. When 4T1 tumor-bearing mice were subjected to NIR irradiation (808 nm) at a power density of 2 cm² for 24 hours, effective tumor elimination was seen. Under laser irradiation,

the temperature in the tumor region increased to 50°C, but the temperature in the non-tumor zone remained normal. More excitingly, in the treated group, no tumor recurrence was seen, and all of the mice lived for almost 40 days without dying [187].

Dai's team created PEGylated GO for cancer treatment to increase the biocompatibility of GO. The PEG-GO with ultra-small size was shown to have extended blood circulation and decreased reticuloendothelial system phagocytosis, resulting in an enhanced PTT effect [188]. Despite the increased biocompatibility, the PTT effectiveness was restricted due to the nonspecific targeting characteristic. As a result, a variety of ligands, such as aptamer, RGD peptide, FA, and HA, have been used in combination with GFNs to improve targeting effectiveness [189]. Lima-Sousa and colleagues, for example, modified RGO with a new HA-based amphiphilic polymer. The nanoparticles were shown to have outstanding biocompatibility and excellent tumor targeting via the CD44 receptor. More crucially, the findings revealed that when exposed to NIR irradiation (808 nm, 1.7 cm²), the nanoparticles may provide an on-demand anti-cancer impact [190]. Similarly, Jun's group coupled GO with FA and CS to create a multifunctional nanoplatform for tumor-targeted PTT guided by NIR fluorescence/photoacoustic imaging. The new nanoplatform was shown to have minimal cytotoxicity even at high concentrations, killing approximately 87 percent of cancer cells when exposed to laser light [191]. Because photo-induced heat created by GFNs can improve medication transport, combining PTT with a chemical therapy or a gene has been proposed as a viable method for improving therapeutic effectiveness [110,192,193]. Thapa and colleagues, for example, created an FA-functionalized GO with irinotecan and docetaxel payloads. As a consequence, the chemo-PTT combination was responsible for 76 percent of deaths, while PTT and chemotherapy alone were responsible for 16 percent and 36 percent of deaths, respectively [194]. Hu et al. also produced RGO sheets with dextran decorations for the delivery of DOX (dubbed RGO/DOX/Dex). Due to the powerful photo-chemotherapy, it was proven that the obtained nanoparticles had greater therapeutic effectiveness after NIR irradiation than single chemotherapy [195]. FA was applied to the surface of RGO/DOX/Dex to achieve more effective photochemotherapy. The good photo-chemotherapy was accomplished as predicted, implying that the decorated RGO nanoparticle has a lot of promise for cancer therapies [196]. Similarly, Yin and colleagues created a new nanoplatform for the delivery of histone deacetylase 1 and K-Ras siRNAs by conjugating FA, NH₂-mPEG-NH₂, and poly-allylamine hydrochloride to the surface of GO. Surprisingly, as compared to the saline-treated group, the combination of PTT and gene therapy resulted in a tumor cell growth rate reduction of over 80% [100]. Furthermore, by conjugating RGO with low molecular weight PEI via a PEG spacer, Kim et al. produced a photothermally regulated gene carrier. The transfection effectiveness of the carrier with laser irradiation was found to be 2 to 3 times higher than that of the control group [197].

Constructing smart carriers for regulated medication release in response to a specific stimulus, such as pH, GSH, or magnetism, is another way to improve the efficacy of PTT. A pH and NIR light-responsive GO composite for photothermally regulated drug delivery of DOX was recently described by Xing et al. With NIR irradiation, more DOX was produced from the composite at pH 5.0 buffer solution than at pH 7.4 buffer solution, resulting in greater cancer cell killing [198]. Using disulfide linkage-linked PEG-modified nanoGO for selective drug release and more effective chemo-PTT, Xiong and colleagues created a GSH-responsive

nanocomplex. The disulfide bond of the nanocomplex was shown to be weakened as a result of the elevated GSH levels inside cancer cells, prompting fast drug release. Surprisingly, NIR irradiation resulted in a 90% inhibition rate of the nanocomplex on the tumor [134]. Yao et al. also developed a GQDs-capped magnetic mesoporous silica (MMSN/GQDs) multifunctional nanocarrier for combined chemo-PTT as a pH and magnetic dual-responsive multifunctional nanocarrier. The drug release was said to be induced by the acidic tumor environment and increased by the hyperthermia temperature created by MMSN/GQDs under an alternating magnetic field and NIR irradiation, resulting in greater tumor cell killing [199].

Increasing data suggests that conjugating GFNs with metal nanoparticles, such as gold (Au) and magnetite nanoparticles, might improve photothermal energy conversion [200,201]. Because of its outstanding features, such as adjustable optical properties, effective light absorption, high biocompatibility, and low cytotoxicity, the Au nanoparticle is one of the ideal photothermal agents to increase the PTT efficacy of GFNs [202,203]. By attaching Au nanoparticles onto GO, which was coated with a Cy5.5-labeled MMP-14 substrate, Gao and associates created a fluorescent/photoacoustic imaging-guided PTT agent. The results showed that the obtained complex's photothermal conversation effectiveness was significantly higher than that of the GO or Au alone. In vivo studies indicated that the combination had a good SCC7 tumor ablation effect with minimal laser radiation and no observable side effects or toxicity [204]. By conjugating RGO/Au with 3-(3-phenylureido) propanoic acid PEG, Ma et al. created a nanohybrid platform (PPEG). This nanohybrid technology outperformed RGO and RGO/PPEG in terms of photothermal conversion efficiency [205]. Magnetite nanoparticles, in addition to Au nanoparticles, have been described as another commonly utilized substance to increase PTT treatment performance. Mousa's team created a graphene magnetite nanocomposite and tested its photothermal properties on HepG2 cancer cells. The photothermal effectiveness of the nanocomposite was shown to be higher than that of RGO and magnetite nanoparticles. Furthermore, by gradually increasing the NIR irradiation period and the nanocomposite concentration, cell survival was reduced [206]. In addition, by putting rice grain-shaped ZnO particles onto graphene triggered with cobalt phthalocyanine, Neelgund and colleagues created an NIR-responsive photothermal agent. The synthesized compound has a better photothermal conversion efficiency than well-known Au- or copper-based photothermal agents. Furthermore, by irradiating with a 980 nm laser for 7 minutes, the compound was shown to be efficient in increasing the temperature up to 68°C and exhibiting a concentration-dependent photothermal action [207].

3.2 PDT

PDT, unlike PTT, is an FDA-approved therapeutic technique for inducing cell apoptosis and/or necrosis that relies on singlet oxygen or other reactive oxygen species (ROS) produced by photosensitizer (PS) molecules under particular light irradiation [30,208,209]. The first-generation PSs, which were complex combinations of porphyrins, were introduced in the 1970s. PSs of the second generation, such as 5-aminolevulinic acid, chlorin, and hypocrellins, have been developed since the 1980s [210–212]. However, because many PSs have long-term photosensitivity, low water solubility, and poor selectivity [213], PSs-loaded drug delivery systems have been developed as a third-generation solution to address these issues [214]. Several nanomaterials, including carbon-based nanoparticles, polymeric nanoparticles, and hydrogels, have recently been utilized as third-generation PSs nanocarriers, resulting in

enhanced therapeutic effectiveness and precision delivery [215,216]. Due to the wide specific surface area and diverse surface functional groups, conjugating conventional photosensitizers with GFNs can maximize the efficiency of PSs and boost their solubility, resulting in an enhanced PDT treatment outcome [217]. Dong's group published the first work on graphene-based PDT. They used stacking and hydrophobic interactions to encapsulate the photosensitizer zinc phthalocyanine (ZnPc) on the surface of the nanoGO-PEG. The loading efficiency of ZnPc has been proven to be as high as 94 percent. After NIR irradiation, the viability of MCF-7 cells treated with nanoGO-mPEG/ZnPc at concentrations ranging from 3.8 to 60 mg/L was dramatically reduced from 80% to 60% [218]. Zhang used stacking to load p-bromophenylhydrazone-methyl pyropheophorbide-A into virgin graphene (termed as G-BPMppa). G-BPMppa was shown to have significantly improved solubility and dispersity in water, as well as a higher singlet oxygen quantum yield (= 60.55 percent) in DMF solution as compared to free BPMppa (29.2 percent) [219]. Hypocrellin-A, a perylenequinonoid hydrophobic non-porphyrin photodynamic anticancer agent, was also bound to the GO in Zhou's laboratory. Because of the increased singlet oxygen generation and high cellular absorption, the obtained nanocomplex was shown to have improved PDT effectiveness [220]. A lot of studies have attempted to chemically or physically alter the GO with targeting ligands to achieve a precise targeting effect [42]. Hu and colleagues, for example, developed a new targeted PS based on FA functionalized GO that loaded ZnO nanoparticles onto its surface. Due to the strong affinity of FA for the Fr receptor overexpressed on HeLa cells, it was discovered that GO-FA-ZnO has a powerful tumor-targeting capability. The obtained nanoparticles were shown to significantly enhance ROS levels in a dose-dependent manner when exposed to visible light. In the cells treated with free ZnO and GO, however, there was no evidence of ROS generation [221].

In another study, pyropheophorbide-a (PPa) was loaded into an integrin $\alpha 3$ monoclonal antibody (mAb) bound to nanoGO to create a mitochondria-targeting PDT agent (termed as PPa-nanoGO-mAb). Because of the mAb-mediated specific targeting effect, the accumulation of PPa in U87-MG cells was significantly improved. More excitingly, because of precise targeting and selective accumulation in the mitochondria, PPa-nanoGO-mAb accumulation increased with time and reached about 80% in 8 hours, resulting in improved photosensitizer pharmacokinetic behavior and decreased side effects [222]. Aside from precise targeting, another major issue for researchers working on GFN-based PDT was increasing its sensitivity to the diseased environment. For PDT, Du et al. used a disulfide bond to attach the photosensitizer Ce6 to the planar structure of GQDs. Ce6 was promptly freed from GQDs as the nanocomplex reached the tumor tissue, and Ce6's photoactivity was recovered. In vivo investigations revealed that GQDs-SS-Ce6 had a stronger inhibitory impact on tumor development than free Ce6 [223]. Xu et al. have created a pH-responsive nanosystem by combining the cationic porphyrin photosensitizer MitoTPP and FA with PEG-functionalized nanoGO. Under acidic pH buffers, the MitoTPP was shown to be released from nanoGO and diffused into mitochondria, resulting in tumor cell death due to excessive ROS production during NIR irradiation [224].

Because GFNs have excellent drug delivery capabilities, combining PDT with chemotherapy has gotten a lot of press recently [225]. For example, in Zhou's research, they created GO nanocomposites for the delivery of hypocrellin A and 7-ethyl-10-hydroxycamptothecin in

order to produce a synergistic impact of PDT and chemotherapy on cancer therapy. The acquired nanocomposites suppressed tumor cell survival effectively, as predicted [226]. Similarly, Huang et al. developed a smart drug delivery system for MutT homolog 1 protein inhibitor and DOX by conjugating GO with PEG, FA, and photosensitizer indocyanine green. The obtained nanoparticle was shown to have improved efficacy in suppressing osteosarcoma cell growth and migration, resulting in a synergistic combination of PDT and chemotherapy [227]. Furthermore, the high levels of ROS generated by PDT were employed as a stimulus signal to regulate medication release. Wang et al., for example, created a dual-responsive NIR and ROS nanocomposite that included diselenide bonds cross-linked to polyamidoamine-pluronic F68 and GO, as well as the payloads of indocyanine green and DOX. The ROS level of MCF-7/ADR cells was observed to be increased by more than 2-fold in the treatment of the nanocomposite following NIR laser irradiation. Intriguingly, increased ROS caused the diselenide link to be cleaved inside tumor cells, resulting in increased drug release and nuclear trafficking of DOX in MCF-7/ADR cells following NIR irradiation [228].

Given GFNs' strong photothermal conversion capacity, combining PDT with PTT might increase photosensitizer distribution and hence anticancer efficacy [229]. Tian et al., for example, produced PEG-functionalized GO for Ce6 delivery. Due to the mild local heating, it was discovered that a low power density 808 nm laser will enable Ce6 delivery. As a consequence, as compared to the free Ce6 or GO-PEG-Ce6 nanocomplex without irradiation, NIR irradiation resulted in more powerful PDT effectiveness against cancer cells [230].

Similarly, Li and colleagues developed a mPEG-GO-C60 hybrid multifunctional nanopatform for synergistic anticancer treatment. Surprisingly, it was discovered that GO may broaden the absorption spectrum of photosensitizer C60, resulting in a strong anti-cancer impact due to PDT and PTT synergism [231]. Arif's group also disclosed a new nanocomposite for upconversion luminescence (UCL) imaging guided combinatorial PDT/PTT treatment that was made by covalently grafting a core-shell structured upconversion nanoparticle with Ce6-loaded nanoGO-PEG. The obtained nanoparticle could not only be used as a UCL imaging probe for diagnostics, but it could also generate ROS when exposed to 808 nm light and convert the photon into heat energy. In vivo findings showed that tumor-bearing mice given the nanoparticle had a significant reduction in tumor growth and a high amount of tumor tissue damage [232]. Zhang et al. created a new nanohybrid for lysosome-targeted phosphorescent imaging and combined PTT/PDT treatment by encapsulating a PEG-modified Ru (II) complex onto the RGO nanosheet (termed RGO-Ru-PEG). RGO-Ru-PEG, as predicted, had good photothermal conversion capacity when exposed to 808 nm light and produced excessive ROS when exposed to 450 nm light. Furthermore, A549 cancer cells may internalize the nanohybrid and selectively target it to lysosomes. In vitro studies show that RGO-Ru-PEG may significantly reduce tumor development when coupled with PTT/PDT therapy [233].

4. Final thoughts

This review described some of the most current biomedical uses of GFNs for drug delivery, gene and drug delivery, PTT, PDT, and multimodal combination treatment in this review paper. GFNs-based nanocarriers have been hailed as one of the most effective carriers for drug delivery due to their unique characteristics, particularly their enormous surface area. The biomedical use of GFNs benefits from rational modification of GFNs with various functional segments because it improves biocompatibility, precise targeting, and site-specific drug

delivery characteristics. GFNs have been investigated in the fields of PTT and light-responsive medication delivery due to their high photothermal conversion capacity. Furthermore, with the help of PSs, GFNs have been shown to be effective in PDT. Several interesting results discussed in this review indicate that GFNs have a bright future in biological applications.

Conclusion

GFNs have been hailed as a rising star in the field of nanomaterials in recent years. GFNs-based nanocomplexes have been widely investigated in the fields of medication delivery and phototherapy, as described in this review. GFNs can be rationally modified with a variety of functional chemicals to improve therapeutic effectiveness. Polymeric modification using friendly and nontoxic chemicals, for example, is a fascinating technique for improving GFN biocompatibility. The active targeted drug delivery of GFNs is facilitated by conjugating with particular targeting ligands.

Furthermore, the stimuli-responsive drug delivery approach may be utilized to precisely control payload release and avoid the negative effects of premature cargo release on normal tissues. For the construction of stimuli-responsive GFNs-based drug delivery devices, differing amounts of metabolic products between healthy and pathological states were taken into account in this method. Nonetheless, endogenous chemicals may not always maintain a constant level, potentially putting cargo release performance in jeopardy. External stimuli-responsive methods for GFNs-based medication delivery devices have been used to solve this challenge. It can deliver a more accurate and controlled medication release from a distance. Furthermore, the GFNs-based code delivery system can maximize the therapeutic impact of both medicines. Furthermore, GFNs' excellent photothermal conversion capacity gives them a lot of potential for PTT with the use of specialized targeting ligands and metal nanoparticles. Furthermore, PDT, a phototherapy method combining GFNs and PSs that may readily cause the formation of ROS with the help of NIR light irradiation, can be accomplished. It's a good way to make tumor cells die through necrosis and apoptosis. Because of the complex microenvironment in the human body, combining numerous materials with different functionalities has been identified as a very fascinating technique and a current trend. As a result, judicious modification of GFNs with functional components or full utilization of GFN-based multimodal combination treatment may have significant biomedical potential. Furthermore, in addition to medication delivery, a recent review study [234] focuses on vaccine delivery using GFNs. During the 2019 coronavirus pandemic, research on GFN-based vaccine delivery systems to combat the outbreak appears to be increasingly important and urgent.

Although several promising pre-clinical accomplishments have been reported in recent years, success in translating GFNs-based nanocomplexes from the bench to the bedside remains a long way off. Low biocompatibility and severe toxicity are the most significant obstacles. GFNs can cause cellular injuries such as cytoskeletal disorder, organelle dysfunction, protein corona damage, and damage to biological macromolecules after being absorbed into the human body, which can lead to a variety of systemic toxic behaviors such as inflammation, lung toxicity, neurotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, blood toxicity, immunotoxicity, and genotoxicity [28]. Numerous studies have shown that coating GFNs with biocompatible polymers on the surface is a viable method for reducing toxicity. To decrease the toxicity of GFNs, biocompatible polymers such as PEG, hyperbranched polyglycerol, -cyclodextrin, and a variety of polysaccharides have been used. Furthermore, the toxicity of GFNs is influenced by

the particle size of GFNs. The smaller GFNs are shown to have more apparent cytotoxicity. Overall, highlighting *in vivo* safety through short- and long-term safety evaluations is critical for GFN clinical applications. Meanwhile, before GFNs are widely used, their influence on the environment should be considered. With the rapid advancement of numerous material sciences, we believe that desired GFNs with minimal negative impacts on the human body and ecology will be manufactured in the future. When combined with successful treatment methods, GFNs have the potential to be used in a variety of clinical applications in biomedicine, including biosensing, bioimaging, tissue engineering, and medication delivery.

A large specific surface area, high Young's modulus, high fracture strength, outstanding electrical and thermal conductivity, and optical absorption are only a few of the physical and chemical characteristics of graphene. GFNs have a high cargo loading capacity and are easy to modify due to their huge specific surface area and many oxygen-containing functional groups. GFNs may be rationally modified with a variety of functional chemicals to improve biocompatibility, minimize inherent toxicity, and accomplish precise targeting, stimuli-responsive drug delivery, drug and gene code delivery, and photodynamic treatment. GFNs can be used for photothermal treatment and light-responsive medication delivery because of their high photothermal conversion capacity.

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